

Polycyclic Systems. Part XII¹. Synthesis of 7-Methoxy-2-oxohydrophenanthrenes

D. Nasipuri and K. K. Biswas,

β -(2-Carboxymethyl-3, 4-dihydro-6-methoxy-1-naphthyl) propionic acid and its aromatic analogue have been synthesised. The dimethyl esters of the acids undergo Dieckmann cyclisation affording 1-methoxycarbonyl-7-methoxy-2-oxohydrophenanthrenes of possible synthetic interest in hydroaromatic steroids. The structure of the cyclisation product has been proved by methylation and subsequent aromatisation into 1-methyl-7-methoxyphenanthrene.

In 1956, we reported a synthesis of 7-methoxy-2-oxohydrophenanthrenes (V & VI)² with a view to exploring the possibility of using them in the synthesis of hydroaromatic steroids. The over-all yield of the ketones, however, was not encouraging and the work was discontinued. Meanwhile an alternative synthesis of the ketone* (V) has been achieved by Japanese group of workers^{3a} who have used it extensively for steroid synthesis. In the present communication, we wish to publish the details of our previous report together with the results of the Dieckmann cyclisation of the esters (as III and IV), as originally intended.

β -(2-Carboxymethyl-3,4-dihydro-6-methoxy-1-naphthyl) propionic acid (III), m.p. 163°, was prepared through a series of reactions starting from ethyl β -oxo-adipate⁴ and *m*-methoxyphenethyl bromide. These two were condensed to give ethyl α -(*m*-methoxyphenethyl)- β -oxo-adipate⁵ which was further alkylated with ethyl bromoacetate in presence of base and the product (I) hydrolysed and re-esterified to furnish the keto-diester (II) in good yield. This was cyclodehydrated with concentrated sulphuric acid according to Robinson and Walker⁶ and the acid (III) obtained in 50% yield. Attempts to improve the yield of cyclisation using other reagents, *e.g.*, polyphosphoric acid⁷, methanolic hydrogen chloride⁸, and *p*-toluenesulphonic acid⁹

* A more recent synthesis has also appeared^{8b}

1. Part XI, D. Nasipuri, D. N. Roy and R. C. Banerjee, *This Journal*, 1963, 40, 225.
2. D. Nasipuri, *Chem. and Ind.*, 1956, 1389.
3. (a) W. Nagata, S. Hirai, T. Terasawa, I. Kikkawa and K. Takeda, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.* (Japan), 1961, 9, 756; also W. Nagata and I. Kikkawa, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1967, 66, 7165.
(b) S. J. Daum, P. E. Shaw and R. L. Clarke, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1967, 32, 1427.
4. J. C. Bardhan, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 1948.
5. J. H. Hunter and J. A. Hogg, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 1922.
6. R. Robinson and J. Walker, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 192.
7. D. Nasipuri, R. Roy and U. Rakshit, *This Journal*, 1960, 37, 369.
8. G. H. Douglas, J. M. H. Graves, D. Hartley, G. A. Hughes, B. J. McLoughlin, J. Siddall and H. Smith, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 5072.
9. J. Martel, E. Toromanoff and C. Huynh, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1965, 30, 1752.

did not succeed, the product in each case being an inseparable mixture. The ester (as III) was aromatised by heating with sulphur to yield β -(2-carboxymethyl-6-methoxy-1-naphthyl) propionic acid (IV), m.p. 175° in good yield.

The dimethyl ester of the acid (III) readily underwent Dieckmann cyclisation with sodium methoxide to yield a β -oxo-ester, m. p. 100-102°, which decomposed gradually on keeping. This on acidic hydrolysis afforded 1,2,3,4,9,10-hexahydro-7-methoxy-2-oxophenanthrene (V) as a gum which subsequently crystallised to a solid, m.p. 75-76°. The ketone was identical with that of Nagata *et al*⁸ and isomeric with the one described by Crowley and Robinson¹⁰. The β -oxo-ester obtained by Dieckmann cyclisation seemed to be a homogeneous product as judged from its crystalline nature

and behaviour in thin layer chromatography and can have two alternative structures (VII & VIII). The structure (VII) seems more probable as it involves the formation of carbanion at a methylene activated both by a methoxy-carbonyl and a styryl group¹¹. Moreover, the resultant enolate anion from (VII) is capable of forming a continuous conjugated system with the aromatic ring. The problem however was easily solved by methylating the sodio-derivative of the β -oxo-ester *in situ*. The product was hydrolysed, the resultant ketone reduced with lithium aluminium hydride, and the crude alcohol dehydrated and dehydrogenated in the usual way. The phenanthrene derivative, m.p. 134°, (trinitrobenzene derivative, m.p. 143°) which was obtained in good yield was identified as 1-methyl-7-methoxyphenanthrene¹². This clearly shows that the Dieckmann reaction product was 1-methoxycarbonyl-2-oxohydrophenanthrene (VII) and not the other isomer (VIII).

The dimethyl ester of the aromatic acid (IV) was likewise submitted to Dieckmann cyclisation. The resultant β -oxo-ester (as VII), m.p. 90-92° was hydrolysed to furnish 2-oxo-7-methoxy-1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydrophenanthrene (VI), m.p. 93°. The β -oxo-ester was also converted into 1-methyl-7-methoxyphenanthrene (IX) in the usual way.

10. G. P. Crowley and R. Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 2001.

11. S. K. Dasgupta and P. C. Antony, *Chem. Comm.*, 1966, 485.

12. W. F. Short, H. Stromberg and A. E. Wiles, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 319.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl β Oxo-adipate :—Ethyl β -oxo-adipate was prepared in large quantity following the general procedure of Guha and Nasipuri as described in Organic Synthesis¹³. In spite of a contrary report¹⁴, the quality of the product was good enough for the present syntheses.

*Ethyl α -(*m*-Methoxyphenethyl)- β -oxo-adipate* :—To a solution of potassium (13.2 g.) in *t*-butanol (330 ml.), was added ethyl β -oxo-adipate (71.3 g.) followed by *m*-methoxyphenethyl bromide (71.3 g.). The mixture was heated under reflux in nitrogen atmosphere for 20 hr. The solvent was then distilled off from a waterbath, the residue cooled, acidified with cold dilute H_2SO_4 and extracted with ether. After removal of the ether, the product was distilled to yield ethyl α -(*m*-methoxyphenethyl)- β -oxo-adipate (68 g. ; 58%), b.p. 210-215°/0.6 mm.

*Ethyl α -(*m*-Methoxyphenethyl)- α -ethoxycarbonylmethyl- β -oxo-adipate (I)* :—To a cold solution of potassium (8.5 g.) in anhydrous *t*-butanol (212 ml.) was added ethyl α -(*m*-methoxyphenethyl)- β -oxo-adipate (67.5 g.). The mixture was brought to room temperature, ethyl bromo-acetate (35 g.) added all at a time and the whole heated under reflux for 16 hr. Most of the solvent was distilled off, the residue decomposed with cold $2NH_3SO_4$, and organic matter extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4), solvent removed, and the residue distilled to give a viscous oil (55 g.), b.p. 210-220°/0.2 mm. A middle fraction was analysed. (Found : C, 63.1 ; H, 7.5 ; $C_{28}H_{32}O_8$ requires C, 63.30 ; H, 7.34%). It did not give any colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

*Methyl 3-(*m*-Methoxyphenethyl)-4-oxopimelate (II)* :—The foregoing ester (55 g.) was refluxed on sandbath with a solution of potassium hydroxide (35 g.) in water (350 ml.) for 30 hr., when an almost homogeneous solution was obtained. This was cooled, neutral material extracted with ether, and the aqueous solution acidified with concentrated HCl. The acidic mixture was boiled on free flame for 1 hr. and then extracted thoroughly with ether. The ethereal extract was once washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4), and the ether removed. The residue (32 g.) was 3-*m*-methoxyphenethyl-4-oxopimelic acid which was not further purified but esterified by boiling with a mixture of absolute methanol (200 ml.) and conc. H_2SO_4 (2 ml.) for 10 hr. The mixture was cooled, diluted with water, and the ester worked up as usual. *Methyl 3-(*m*-methoxyphenethyl)-4-oxopimelate (II)* was obtained as a colourless oil (25 g.), b.p. 185-190°/0.2 mm. (Found : C, 63.9 ; H, 7.5. $C_{18}H_{24}O_6$ requires C, 64.28 ; H, 7.14%). A portion of the ester was hydrolysed but the resultant acid could not be induced to crystallise.

β -(2-Carboxymethyl-3, 4-dihydro-6-methoxy-1-naphthyl) propionic Acid (III) :—The preceding ester (2 g.) added dropwise to concentrated H_2SO_4 (9 ml.) cooled

13. M. Guha and D. Nasipuri, *Org. Synth.*, 1962, 42, 41.

14. E. C. Taylor and A. McKillop, *Tetrahedron*, 1967, 23, 897.

to -15° with mechanical stirring. A deep reddish brown solution resulted which was stirred at -15° for 3 hr. and then poured over crushed ice. The organic matter was thoroughly extracted with ether, the ethereal extract once washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4), and solvent evaporated. The residual oil (1.8 g.) was hydrolysed with 10% ethanolic potassium hydroxide. The *acid* (III) was worked up in the usual way and obtained as a solid (0.95 g.), m.p. $158-160^{\circ}$. It crystallised from aqueous methanol in white needles, m.p. 163° . (Found: C, 66.2; H, 6.5; equiv. 144. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 66.2; H, 6.2%; equiv. 145).

The acid (4.3 g.) was esterified by refluxing with a mixture of methanol (30 ml.) and concentrated H_2SO_4 (0.3 ml.) for 10 hr. The *methyl ester* was obtained as a viscous oil (4.1 g.), b.p. $185-190^{\circ}/0.2$ mm. (Found: C, 67.7; H, 7.2. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 67.92; H, 6.91%).

β -(2-Carboxymethyl-6-methoxy-1-naphthyl)propionic Acid (IV):—The above ester (4.0 g.) was intimately mixed with powdered sulphur (0.44 g.) and heated in a nitre-nitrate bath at 250° for 2 hr. The brown liquid was taken up in benzene, refluxed with precipitated copper for a few hours, filtered, and benzene removed. The residue was hydrolysed with 10% alcoholic potassium hydroxide and acid worked up in the usual way. β -(2-Carboxymethyl-6-methoxy-1-naphthyl)propionic acid (IV) (3.2 g.) thus obtained had m.p. $155-160^{\circ}$. This crystallised from methanol in fine needles, m.p. 175° . (Found: C, 66.2; H, 5.8; equiv., 144. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 66.66; H, 5.55%; equiv., 144).

The *dimethyl ester* was prepared in the usual way and was obtained as a colourless oil, b.p. $190^{\circ}/0.2$ mm. (Found: C, 68.0; H, 6.5. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 68.35, H, 6.33%).

Dieckmann Cyclisation of Methyl β -(2-Methoxycarbonylmethyl-3, 4-dihydro-6-methoxy-1-naphthyl)propionate:—The dimethyl ester (1.9 g.) of the unsaturated acid (III) was added to finely divided sodium (0.2 g.) suspended in dry benzene (10 ml.). The reaction was initiated by the addition of a drop of methanol and completed by refluxing on the waterbath for 4 hr. under nitrogen. The mass solidified into a cake which was cooled in ice and decomposed with dilute H_2SO_4 . The benzene layer was separated, washed with water, dried, and the solvent evaporated. The residue solidified to a crystalline mass, m.p. $100-102^{\circ}$. This was not analysed since it showed sign of decomposition on keeping but was directly hydrolysed¹⁵ by heating with a mixture of acetic acid (10 ml.), concentrated HCl (5 ml.) and water (1 ml.) on a sandbath for 1 hr. The solution was diluted with water, the organic matter collected in ether, and the ethereal extract washed repeatedly with sodium bicarbonate solution. The residue after evaporation of the solvent was once passed through a column of alumina in benzene solution and afforded 1, 2, 3, 4, 9, 10-hexahydro—7-methoxy—2-oxo-phenanthrene (0.8 g.) as a solid. This crystallised from

benzene petroleum in white needles, m.p. 75-76° (Found : C, 78.5 ; H, 7.2. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{16}O_2$; C, 78.94 ; H, 7.02%) (Lit.⁸ m.p. 78-78.5°). The *dinitrophenylhydrazone* obtained in the usual way had m.p. 205° (Found : C, 61.5 ; H, 5.2 ; N, 13.4. $C_{21}H_{20}O_6N_4$ requires C, 61.76 ; H, 4.90 ; N, 13.72%). The I.R. spectra of the ketone had carbonyl absorption at 1720 cm^{-1} .

Methylation of the β -Oxo-ester (VII). Formation of 1-Methyl-7-methoxyphenanthrene (IX). In another experiment the dimethyl ester (1.9 g.) of the acid (III) was treated with finely divided sodium dispersed in benzene as described before. The solid cake so formed was cooled, an excess of methyl iodide added and the mixture refluxed on the waterbath for 4 hr. The product was worked up in the usual way, organic matter extracted with benzene, washed with sodium bisulphite solution and water, dried, and the solvent evaporated. A viscous oil (2.0 g.) was obtained which did not give any colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. It was hydrolysed by refluxing with a solution of potassium hydroxide (2 g.) in water (20 ml.) on a sandbath under nitrogen for 10 hr. The solution was then acidified, organic matter extracted with ether, and the solvent evaporated. To ensure the completion of hydrolysis and decarboxylation, the residue was further treated with a boiling mixture of glacial acetic acid (4 ml.), concentrated HCl (2 ml.), and water (0.5 ml.) for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. The mixture was diluted, extracted with ether, and the ethereal extract washed with sodium bicarbonate solution until free from acid. The solvent was evaporated to give 1-methyl-7-methoxy-2-oxohexahydrophenanthrene as a gum (0.8 g.) This was taken up in benzene and the solution eluted through an alumina column. An almost colourless oil (0.7 g.) was obtained which could not be crystallised and possibly consisted of a mixture of Δ^{4a-10a} and Δ^{1-10a} isomers, the latter predominating.

The above oil (0.5 g.) was reduced with an ethereal solution of lithium aluminium hydride and the crude alcohol thus obtained was dehydrated by heating with anhydrous formic acid (1.5 ml.) at 100° for 45 min. Formic acid was removed at the water pump and the residue sublimed at 180°/0.4 mm to give a clear viscous liquid (0.45 g.). This was intimately mixed up with 10% palladium-charcoal (0.1 g.) and heated at 280° for 2 hr. The solid mass was extracted repeatedly with hot benzene and the benzene solution filtered. The filtrate was evaporated to dryness and the solid residue (0.4 g.) sublimed at 200-210°/0.4 mm to furnish shining white crystals of 7-methoxy-1-methylphenanthrene (0.31 g.). One crystallisation from methanol afforded colourless flakes, m.p. 134° (Found : C, 86.3 ; H, 6.4. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{14}O$: C, 86.5 ; H, 6.3%) ; Lit¹² reports m.p. 133.5-134.5°. The trinitrobenzene derivative formed readily and crystallised from ethanol-benzene in bright yellow needles, m.p. 143° (Found : C, 60.5 ; H, 4.0. Calc. for $C_{22}H_{17}N_3O_7$; C, 60.7 ; H, 3.9%) ; Lit¹⁶ m.p. 143-145.5°.

1, 2, 3, 4-Tetrahydro-7-methoxy-2-oxophenanthrene (VI) : The dimethyl ester (2.3 g.) of the aromatic acid (IV) was heated on a steam bath with finely divided

sodium (0.22 g.) in benzene (10 ml.) and a drop of methanol for 4 hr. under nitrogen. The product was worked up in the usual way. The cyclic β -oxo-ester (2.1 g.), thus obtained, melted at 90-92°. It was hydrolysed with a refluxing mixture of glacial acetic acid (10 ml.), concentrated HCl (5 ml.), and water (1 ml.) for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. 1, 2, 3, 4-Tetrahydro-7-methoxy-2-oxophenanthrene (VI), so obtained, was crystallised from methanol in white flakes (0.9 g.), m.p. 93° (Found : C, 79.4 ; H, 6.5. $C_{15}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 79.64 ; H, 6.19%). It gave a crystalline *semicarbazone*, m.p. 189° (Found : N, 14.5. $C_{16}H_{17}O_2N_3$ requires N, 14.84%), and a *dinitrophenylhydrazone*, m.p. 246° (Found : C, 61.8 ; H, 4.5. $C_{21}H_{18}N_4O_6$ requires C, 62.07 ; H, 4.43%).

In another experiment, the β -oxo-ester obtained after Dieckmann cyclisation was methylated, hydrolysed, and reduced as described in an analogous case. The crude alcohol was dehydrated with formic acid and finally dehydrogenated with 10% palladium-charcoal to afford 7-methoxy-1-methylphenanthrene, m.p. and mixed m.p. 133°.

Thanks are due to Mrs. Chhabi Dutta, at present of the Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Calcutta for micro-analysis and Dr. S. C. Pakrasi of the Indian Institute of Experimental Medicine, Calcutta for I. R. spectra.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE,
92, ACHARYA PRAFULLA CHANDRA ROAD,
CALCUTTA-9

Received, September 28, 1967.